

Supplemental Materials - Methods

Vibrio cholerae initial growth on Sigma Type III porcine gastric mucin.

Strains were grown on LB + 0.1mg/mL streptomycin plates overnight at 37°C and a single colony isolate used to start a fresh LB + 0.1mg/mL streptomycin broth culture grown overnight 210rpm at 37°C. Overnight cultures were washed in PBS and resuspended to an optical density 1.0 OD₆₀₀. 700µl of either LB, MCLMAN + 0.5% Mucin (Sigma Type III porcine gastric mucin), or MCLMAN minimal media was inoculated 1:1000 with the 1.0 OD₆₀₀ culture. Triplicate 200µl aliquots were dispensed in a 96-well plate and optical densities recorded every 30min for 24h.

Complementation plasmid construction

Complementation plasmid construct open reading frame inserts were generated by PCR using Phusion high-fidelity polymerase (Thermo Scientific). pMMB66EH vector backbones were generated by plasmid purification using Qiagen Mini Prep Kit and subsequent restriction digested using BamHI and HindIII at 37°C for 1 hour followed by an additional 30 minutes at 37°C with alkaline phosphatase from calf intestine (CIP) (New England Biolabs). Constructs were assembled using Gibson assembly (New England Biolabs) and were electroporated into electrocompetent S17 λpir *E. coli* and recovered on LB + 0.1mg/mL ampicillin agar plates.

Vibrio cholerae complementation strain construction

Complementation strains were made by mating S17 λ pir *E. coli* pMMB66EH complementation strains with $\Delta aceE$, $\Delta aceF$, and $\Delta pflA$ mutant strains and recovered on LB + 0.1mg/mL ampicillin + 25 U/mL polymyxin B agar plates. Strains were verified using pMMB66EH plasmid-specific primers to detect the full length insert and additional sequencing primers to verify construct sequence.

Complementation growth curves for $\Delta aceE$ and $\Delta aceF$

M9 + 0.5% glucose was prepared and 2mL prewarmed media inoculated 1:250 with 1.0 OD₆₀₀ culture and grown 210rpm at 37°C. For wild type control and $\Delta aceE$ complementation strains, 1mM isopropyl- β -D-thiogalactoside (IPTG) was added to induce ectopic expression from the complementation vector. For the $\Delta aceF$ complementation strain, 0.01mM IPTG was added to induce vector expression. At each timepoint, 100 μ l was removed for dilution series plating.

Complementation growth curves for $\Delta pflA$

M9 + 0.5% glucose 50mM fumarate media was prepared and 700 μ l was inoculated 1:250 with 1.0 OD₆₀₀ culture. Triplicate 200 μ l aliquots were dispensed in a 96-well plate and grown statically at 37°C in anaerobic conditions. Optical densities were recorded every 1h for 24h. For both WT control and *pflA* complementation strains, 1mM isopropyl- β -D-thiogalactoside (IPTG) was added to induce ectopic expression from the complementation vector.